

3rd order shim for high resolution fMRI at 7T: It hurts more than it helps

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Synopsis (100 words, without titles)

Motivation: 3rd order B₀-shimming at high resolution 7T fMRI can mitigate geometric distortions. But the corresponding shim coils can induce field perturbations when mechanical resonances are excited (Boulant 2024).

Goal: We aim to investigate the advantages and disadvantages of 3rd order shimming on high resolution fMRI across scanners and sequences.

Approach: We compared EPI artifacts (Fuzzy Ripples) and geometric distortions with and without 3rd order shims in N=15 scans.

Results: We find that for high-resolution fMRI protocols, it is best to conduct experiments without 3rd order shims. Shims should be physically disconnected.

Impact: The results presented here inform the UHF-fMRI community about a simple trick to improve the data quality: disconnecting 3rd order shim coils.

Purpose

B0-homogenization with 3rd order shim coils has the potential to mitigate geometrical distortions in EPI-based imaging. This is particularly relevant for high-resolution fMRI at 7T. Thus, almost all modern 7T scanners are equipped with gradient sets that include a few 3rd order shim coils. GE/SIEMENS 7T scanners commonly are equipped with: Z^3 , Z^2X , Z^2Y , $Z(X^2-Y^2)$.

Recently, Boulant et al. (2024) found that there can be inductive coupling between 3rd order shim coils and imaging gradients when mechanical resonances are excited. This can result in k-space trajectory imperfections (Fig. 1B). See (Boulant 2024) for details.

Independently, in previous work of our group, we have shown that high-resolution functional imaging can be significantly limited by EPI trajectory imperfections that manifest in the form of Fuzzy Ripples; low spatial frequency shading patterns (Huber 2024). In this study, we hypothesize that the Fuzzy Ripples are largely caused by the coupling mentioned above.

We seek to investigate quantitatively the impact of 3rd order shim coils on high resolution EPI quality and whether the challenging Fuzzy Ripple artifacts can be mitigated by simply disconnecting 3rd order shims.

Methods

We tested the effect of 3rd order shims on three 7T SIEMENS scanners (two 7T Terras and one 7T Plus). We tested a series of sequences that are commonly used for high resolution fMRI: 2D Multiband from CMRR (Moeller 2010), the SIEMENS product ep2d, and the DZNE 3D-EPI (Stirnberg 2021). Representative axial protocols were tested with typical echo spacings between 1ms and 1.3ms, outside of the vendor-imposed forbidden bands, as needed to balance demands of necessarily large matrix sizes with appropriate echo times.

Each protocol was tested with and without 3rd order shims connected (Fig. 1C). For the disconnected setups, the scanner measurement configuration was adjusted to exclude high order terms in the vendor provided 3D B0-shimming procedure. With each setup, the same automatic shim procedure, optimized for the brain, was applied before imaging.

Practical steps of safely switching off the 3rd order shims and sequence executions are described on the layer-fMRI blog: <https://layerfmri.com/3rdordershim>.

N=15 in-vivo scan sessions were conducted with local IRB approval.

Results

We find that the previously reported Fuzzy Ripples are always visible in the imaging volume across scanners and sequences (arrows in Fig. 2). These artifacts are mitigated when 3rd order shims are disconnected.

We find that these artifacts are not limited to static EPI signal intensity biases, but rather these artifacts have a significant detrimental effect on the temporal fMRI stability. Fig. 3 exemplifies two cases of auditory activation mapping. It can be seen that the activation maps are incomplete when the 3rd order shims are connected.

We find that the geometrical distortions in EPI are qualitatively not substantially improved by the application of 3rd order shimming. The typical biologically induced distortion patterns do not match the spatial modes that the 3rd order shims can account for to begin with (Fig. 4). The average voxels-shift is 1.5mm(\pm 0.5mm) with the 3rd order shim and 1.8mm (\pm 0.7mm) without the 3rd order shim, respectively.

Discussion

We show that the omnipresent Fuzzy Ripple artifacts of layer-fMRI protocols are generally improved when disconnecting the 3rd order shims, across sequences and 7T scanner models. When they are plugged, when vibrating a current is induced in them by Faraday's law which most likely couples back to the gradient by mutual inductance and leads to field perturbations.

Disconnecting the 3rd order shim improved the image quality, but it can be accompanied with inconvenient changes to the institutional MR-scanning workflow. Namely, the vendor-provided 3D shimming routine needs to be adjusted so that it optimizes the 1st and 2nd-order shim terms in conjunction with the 3rd order status. Depending on how this is done, it requires a partial reboot of scanner sub-systems (5-15 min). While the vendor has user-friendly procedures for this, it is advised to do this after consulting the local vendor service engineers. Fig. 5 indicates alternative approaches to work around "fuzzy ripple" artifacts. For instance, the readout-polarity-dependent artifact can be estimated using a dual-polarity prescan and retrospectively corrected for in the complex-valued images.

Summary

We find that 3rd order shims can introduce EPI trajectory errors at some echo spacings that reduce the image quality of high resolution fMRI data. While there is a small reduction in geometric distortions with the 3rd order shim, the overall image quality and fMRI activation detectability is much improved without 3rd order shims. Until the vendors release an anticipated fix for the 3rd-order shim-induced trajectory errors, we conclude that its best to unplug the 3rd order shims for all of our higher res fMRI scans. It remains always advised to optimize echo-spacings.

Acknowledgements (no work count limit)

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5 Figures (500 characters per caption)

One synopsis figure:

Abstract figures:

Fig. 1: Background of 3rd order shim in 7T fMRI

Panel A) depicts the spatial symmetry of the windings patterns of imaging gradients and the 3rd order shim coils. This symmetry can result in inductive coupling with corresponding imperfections of imaging gradient trajectories.

Panel B) shows published examples of this across three 7T scanners (7T Terra and 7T Iseult with 3rd order shim coils plugged, versus 7T classic Magnetom with 3rd order shims unplugged).

Panel C) Disconnecting parts of the circuit inside the Faraday cage can mitigate these problems.

Fig. 2: Image artifacts across high resolution fMRI protocols across sequences and scanners

Panel A) depicts Fuzzy Ripple artifacts (red arrows) as they are common in almost all sub-millimeter fMRI protocols. Here compared across EPI sequences.

These artifacts are mitigated to a large extent after disconnecting the 3rd order shim coils.

Panel B) shows that these artifacts are consistent across all three tested 7T scanners. The artifacts are gone, when disconnecting the 3rd order shims.

Fig. 3: How 3rd order shim coils affect high resolution activation maps.

This figure shows activation maps of two participants for an auditory block-designed task. It can be seen that the activation map is more complete when 3rd order shims are disconnected. The temporal instability caused by 3rd-order-shim-induced Fuzzy Ripple artifacts hides some parts of the activation below the threshold.

For corresponding time series movies see: <https://layerfmri.page.link/stability>.

Fig. 5: Alternative ways to account for 3rd order shim issues

We investigated if the effect of 3rd order shim induced trajectory imperfections can be mitigated without opening the circuit by unplugging the cables via three strategies:

- A)** EPI dual-polarity calibration can mitigate the fuzzy ripple artifact despite 3rd order shims.
- B)** Changing the EPI echo spacing can mitigate the artifacts too, but then with less choice for the user.
- C)** Dual polarity GRAPPA does not seem to mitigate the artifact effectively.